
LISTENING IN THE WIDER CONTEXT

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Abstract: Listening, often regarded as a foundational skill in language acquisition, extends beyond mere comprehension to significant implications in broader contexts. This paper explores the multifaceted role of listening within educational, social, and professional settings. It highlights the importance of active listening and its impact on effective communication, collaboration, and interpersonal relationships. By examining various listening strategies and assessment methods, the study demonstrates how fostering strong listening skills can enhance overall language proficiency and contribute to cognitive development. Furthermore, it discusses challenges learners face in diverse environments and presents practical solutions for educators to support listening skill development. Ultimately, this work advocates for a comprehensive approach to listening that recognizes its value in facilitating engagement and understanding across various life contexts.

Keywords: Wider context, integrated listening, self-assessment, webquests, chanting, language labs.

The context is the situation of the listening text. So this will give you a lot of extra information to help you in the test. The more you know about the situation, the easier it is to help you imagine the scene. The context can help you think about what

the speakers are saying. Listening goes beyond hearing sounds; it involves understanding, interpreting, and responding effectively. In various contexts—personal relationships, workplaces, or community interactions—effective listening fosters deeper connections and enhances communication. Integrated listening. As we have seen in previous chapters, the four skills reading, writing, speaking and listening rarely take place in isolation. What would writers be without readers! Even private diaries are read, perhaps years later, by their own writers. What would speakers be without listeners? Here's one answer to that question: when Britain's Prince Charles admitted that he spoke regularly to his plants, some British newspapers concluded, not altogether seriously, that he was mad. The majority of EFL and ESL lessons, certainly in general English classes, incorporate all four of the skills, plus grammar, vocabulary and pronunciation, in varying patterns and ratios. Classes may take the form of speak-listen-speak or speak-read-write-speak or read-vocabulary-speak or, in some cases, grammar-grammar-grammar. Sometimes the lesson may focus almost exclusively on one skill or aspect of the language. For example, if you are preparing a class for a written exam, it may be valid to have the students writing for a large chunk of the lesson. Furthermore, there are programmes - in many intensive English courses in US universities, for instance which separate the skills into listening classes, speaking classes, writing classes, and so on. Here we will argue that a balance of skills is desirable for any one lesson, and that the teaching of listening when integrated with other skills.¹

Listening in the Wider Context: An Indication of Integrating Assessment into Listening Instruction to be pronunciation characteristics The first syllable of over 80% of English words with multiple syllables is stressed. This understanding helps native listeners subconsciously recognise word boundaries or where words start and end. Non native listeners might not be able to perceive this unless

¹ How to teach listening skill.

they have an intense passion for the English language's rhythms. The rhythms of a language are audible to humans and may even be felt even before they are born since they can perceive sound before birth. After then, it is inferred subliminally that this beat is universal. In English, stressed syllables can be up to three times longer than unstressed ones. However, in Italian and Spanish, the difference in length between stressed and unstressed syllables is only slightly noticeable. Because of this, emphasis on stress during early listening and pronunciation instruction is crucial for introducing students to the English language's rhythm. Many of the issues non-native English speakers have to comprehend native speakers have less to do with how they produce particular sounds and more to do with how they have not learned the rhythm of the language.

According to research, in order to comprehend the aural information, students must successfully employ their learning techniques and skills. Typically, these techniques are created to aid students in various academic disciplines. "By using instructional techniques as one of the most effective solutions for learners who are dealing with some learning difficulties, strategy instruction is a good answer and often vital to students' success" (Beckman, 2002, Reid & Lienemann, 2006), 12 learners are aware of the various listening aids that can enhance your ability to listen effectively. Teachers should motivate students to engage in utilising the powerful techniques described in this study.²

Self-assessment is closely linked with learner independence. If students become more autonomous, they can measure their own development and take the necessary steps to improve. Four hours of English lessons per week (the average in many contexts) is not enough, particularly when it comes to the difficulties of listening.

²https://www.researchgate.net/publication/372344151_Listening_in_the_Wider_Context_An_Indication_of_Integrating_Assessment_into_Listening_Instruction

Recent technological developments, such as webquests - structured projects using listening texts and downloads on the Internet - allow students access to listening material, but they may need training in what to do with it. To this end, students might benefit from frameworks or generic tasks. These might include writing down words they understood, writing a summary or completing a Who/Where/What/When chart (see page 120). There might also be a link to critical thinking; you could ask the students to listen/watch and rate the content, something that is done already on www.youtube.com, one of the world's most popular websites. YouTube is a useful resource in that it allows anyone to post their video clips. As a result, there is an enormous choice, and many are accessible.

In fact, the choice on the net may be bewildering. One solution is to do some 'flood listening'. Flood listening consists of students choosing one topic and listening to everything they can find about it (they get a flood of input). Naturally, the students will choose either something they are interested in or a topic they need to research for academic purposes. An incidental benefit of flood listening is that certain words and expressions will keep recurring - an excellent aid to vocabulary acquisition.³

Encouraging the learners to listen to podcasts for fun choosing the ones that suit their interests or meet their needs. I always have something to suggest from the sea of podcasts available now. For example:

Upper-intermediate and advanced: [Scott Mills Daily](#), [Best Bits with Greg James](#),

Pre-intermediate and Intermediate: [6 Minute English](#), [BBC Outlook](#)

They can listen on their way to/from school or work, whenever they have some free time.

³ How to teach listening skill.

- “Chanting” technique for songs; I also call this “rhythmic reading”. A student chooses a song to his/her taste, then gets the lyrics and listens to the song reading the lyrics. After that they read the lyrics out loud as close as possible to the rhythm of the song also paying attention to the pronunciation and intonation. That is quite a challenge and a great fun!
- How often do we just listen, without seeing people and interacting with them? Well, from my observations, that happens quite seldom, even classical phone calls tend to be replaced by video calls in messengers. Why practice just listening so much then? the video is to be used more often than listening now! Students can choose shows they like and make use of the translation and subtitles.

So, to recap it all:

- Students often do not listen enough outside the classroom, and that is a problem!
- Nowadays the video plays even a more important role for learning than classical audio tracks.
- It is important to make listening practice fun, natural and well-adjusted to the tastes and interests of the students.⁴

Activities conducted in the language labs to improve listening skills

- Marking items in a picture - Having carried out some pre-listening work using a picture, students are asked to respond to various stimuli by marking things on the picture like – identifying people and things, marking items mentioned by the teacher, marking errors, checking details and marking choices etc.

⁴ <https://www.teachingenglish.org.uk/professional-development/teachers/knowning-subject/magazine/more-listening-practice-outside>

- Information gap activities – Students are given comic strips with dialogue boxes. Students listen to the teacher and fill in the boxes with appropriate dialogues
- Situational dialogues – With a pre-listening activity as to what or where the situation is (information counters, at the doctors, academic counseling etc), the students listen to conversations and fill in with appropriate dialogues, figures and facts.
- Group Discussion video – The faculty talks about the characteristics of a group and discussion and shows a video on it. The students actively listen and answer questions on it later. The teacher discusses the answers with the students and furthers clarifies doubts.
- Text completion - This is an information transfer exercise. We give the students plenty of time to go through the text. Because some weak learners tend to get left behind, there are only a few gaps for completion. Newspaper articles and short excerpts of a story are taken as these work well with students.
- Listening comprehension – Tests from TOEFL and IELTS are taken. Students are given the questions to go through first and then the recording is played with intermittent gaps. The students answer the questions and then the teacher discusses the answers. We also try to find out where the students may have gone wrong and why as these lessons are sometimes difficult to follow because of the accent.
- Film Review – Students are shown movies like ‘Gandhi’, ‘Men of Honor’, ‘Pursuit of Happyness’. As pre-listening we give an introduction to the movie with brief character sketches so that it would facilitate better understanding.⁵

⁵<https://www.pramanaresearch.org/gallery/prj-p492.pdf>

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